

Affordances of distractors and compatibility effects: a study with the computational model TROPIICALS

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Compatibility effect experiments demonstrate that seeing an object activates both visual and action representations in the brain. Compatibility effects experiments in the presence of a distractor object show that responding to a target with a grip compatible with the size of the distractor produced slower RTs in comparison to the incompatible case [1]. This work presents an enhanced version of the TROPIICALS model [2] that reproduces and explains these results. This explanation is based on the idea that the prefrontal cortex (PFC) plays a double role in its top-down guidance of action selection [3]: (a) a positive bias in favor of the action requested by the experimental task; (b) a negative bias directed to inhibiting the action evoked by the distractor. The suppression of the actions elicited by the distractor, eventually sharing common parameters with the action requested by the experimental task, explains the inverted compatibility effect of distractors. The model also provides testable predictions on target and distractor compatibility effects in Parkinson disease patients [4][5] (data not reported).

Model Architecture

Embodied test

Results

Interpretation: competition in PMC

The four core principle of the TROPIICALS model

Results and conclusions:

The model successfully reproduces and explains the target data on the complex interplay between the target and distractor affordances based on a double excitatory/inhibitory role exerted by the PFC on the premotor cortex (PMC) [3]. These results corroborate the hypothesis that compatibility effects related to the target object mainly involve excitatory influence of the PFC on the PMC (via the supplementary motor cortex and the anterior intraparietal area, AIP), whereas the effects related to distractors involve inhibitory aspects of them.

References

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